

OPINION OF MENTOR TEACHERS ON INTERNSHIP PROGRAMME

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Abstract

The paper deals with the impact of B.Ed. internship programme on regular school schedule. In this sense the study objects to detect the opinion of mentor teachers about the internship programme. To reveal this, the study is confined to the supportive schools of NDWCTE, Bhubaneswar. There is very little, or no research conducted in India in general and in Orissa in particular to identify the effect of internship programme. The particular interest of this study was to seek information regarding the internship programme as the opinion of teachers. To develop the understanding of the different problems, views and suggestions of teachers related to internship programme.

Keywords: *Internship programme, Interrelationship, Responsibility, Timing, Effect on school children, Effect on schoolteacher.*

INTRODUCTION

Quality Education in India is increasingly being perceived as a crucial significance, capable of modifying the economic scenario and transforming for dream of millions of Indians for a better and higher quality of life into a reality. In this context, effective teacher education programme is the problematic indicator for quality teaching in Secondary schools, Elementary Teacher Education institutions and District institute of Educational Trainings.

A nation is built by its citizens-citizens are moulded by teachers and teachers are made by teacher educations. The NPE 1986 has rightly stated, "No people can rise above the level of its teachers". So for the development of the country, it is very important to have a good system of teacher education and dedicated, efficient teacher educators.

From this point of view the teacher preparation programme assumes greater importance. The quality and success of any educational system depend upon teachers and the quality of teacher depends upon the teacher education programme. The Education Commission (1964-

66) stressed that in a world based on science and technology, it is education that determines the level of prosperity, welfare and security of the people and that a social programme of professional education of teachers is essential for the qualitative improvement of education.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To collect the opinion of schoolteachers on different dimensions of internship programme.
- To find out the difference in opinion with regard to more experienced and less experienced teachers.
- To find out the difference in opinion with regard to male and female teachers.
- To find out the suggestions of schoolteachers towards the internship programme.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

- There exists no significant difference in opinion regarding the effect of internship programme between more experienced & less experienced teachers.
- There exists no significant difference in opinion regarding the effect of internship programme between male & female teacher.

THE METHOD OF STUDY

Design of the study

The present study was worked out through survey method and necessary information and perception was collected through questionnaire.

Population and sample

Population-

9 Govt. schools (supportive schools of NDWCTE, BBSR) of Bhubaneswar.

All the teachers of nine govt. High schools of Bhubaneswar (Approximately 200 teachers).

Total population =200

Sample @ 30%=60 (51 teachers & 9 Head teachers)

This study had three stage sampling procedure.

N =60 (Total sample)

33 teachers – Experienced (more than 6 years)

18 teachers – Less experienced (less than 6 years)

9 Head teachers

1st, 2nd & 3rd group were again divided into male or female so as to find out the difference in opinion if any in relation to sex.

Procedure of data collection

Questionnaire prepared by the investigator was responded by the school teachers. The

researcher was took all possible care in explaining regarding the mode of responses to the respondents before the administration of the questionnaire. She was personally visit the schools to collect their opinion

Data Analysis:

Mean, standard deviation, T - test, percentage was used and qualitative analysis also adopted for analysing & interpreting the data.

MAJOR FINDINGS

- The teachers opinion are positive or good towards Responsibility, Interrelationship and Timing dimensions and average towards Effect on school children & Effect on school teacher dimensions.
- There is no significant difference between the opinion of more experienced and less experienced teachers on responsibility, interrelationship, timing and effect on school teacher dimensions. But there is significant difference between the opinion of more experienced and less experienced teachers on effect on school children dimension.
- There is no any significant difference between the opinion of male & female of more experienced and less experienced teachers on different dimensions.
- Most of the teacher's opinion are positive towards the responsive behaviour of pupil teachers. Some teacher's opinion is also satisfactory and it should be improve in dealing with the senior teachers as well as the non-teaching staffs of the institution.
- The interrelationship between students, pupil teachers & teachers is fairly good, cordial & harmonious as the views of most of the teachers. Some teachers also give satisfactory response about the interrelationship.
- School students enjoy the teaching of pupil teachers due to the using of variety teaching aids and also different methods, according to most of the teachers view. Some teachers view is also satisfactory that internship programme is not always beneficial for the school students. Students learning and understanding about a particular subject is depend on the capability of a particular pupil teacher.
- From the pupil teachers some teacher come to know about the information of new methods. Some teachers view is that they already known about the new information by their periodical training.
- There are various suggestions given by school teachers as:

About the stipend of pupil teacher for the internship period, to extend the duration of internship programme, proper training and guidance should be provided to pupil teachers for their effective teaching, pupil teachers should have to use ICT, project, practical, local or

handmade TLM, completion of course, supervisors have to supervise every classes.

CONCLUSION

The teacher is the yardstick that measures the achievement and aspirations of the nation the worth and potentialities of a country get evaluated in and through the work of a teacher, “the people of country are the enlarged replica of their teachers”. They are the real nation builder. Teaching is an intricate, exciting and challenging profession. It is the teaching profession, which helps an individual for his growth fully, in his body, mind, spirit, intellectual emotion and with moral values and artistic sensitivity. Therefore, teaching has been accepted as the noblest profession. Internship programme is the first and best experience of pupil teachers for the teaching profession. So teacher educators have to perfectly build them for this programme and check them during the programme. If both school and college of Teacher Education cooperate, effective teacher can be built for our future generation.

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